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Owned media, influencer marketing, and unofficial brand ambassadors: differences between narratives, types of prescribers, and effects on interactions on Instagram

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In the current era of the attention economy, users find themselves in social networks oversaturated with advertising that tends not to catch the public's attention or have great credibility. In this sense, brands are trying to get closer to their audiences by using non-invasive, user-generated storytelling strategies with a more natural and experience-focused message. This research aims to compare which narrative elements used by the official accounts of 5 Ibero-American nation brands on Instagram and by the users (UGC) of hashtags promoted from those official accounts generate greater organic interaction on that social network (likes and comments). With a correlational view, we seek to compare whether the promotion of countries generates greater interaction between those generated by owned media and by users (UGC). For this purpose, two analysis sheets were designed and validated to perform quantitative, descriptive, and correlational content analysis and were applied, on the one hand, to 5 official profiles of Ibero-American countries (Argentina, Ecuador, Mexico, Panama, and Venezuela) and on the other hand, using the hashtags promoted from these official accounts, the 100 posts of user-generated content (UGC) with greater relevance according to the platform were chosen. The main results show that Reels reach almost five times higher than any other type of posts in UGC accounts, while on the contrary, in corporate accounts, they are the types of content with the least interactions. Unlike what one might think, contests (giveaways) on official accounts generated fewer likes and social responsibility content, and posts featuring influencers and celebrities also failed to achieve significant interactions. Overall, official accounts generate the same amount of likes as UGC but significantly fewer comments. Brands only outperform UGC in likes in individual Photographs or Photo Rolls, while UGC outperforms brands in Reels for both metrics.

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Finally, concerning RQ3, UGC posts have been shown to generate more comments than owned media by a factor of at least four overall and for Mexico. Considering all five countries and all types of posts, there is no significant statistical difference for like generation, but there are some cases where these smaller groups show differences. Owned media generates more likes in the single Photograph and Photograph Roll type posts, but it is important to note that these types of posts are far below Reels in popularity for users. This popularity difference can also be seen in the interactions generated for Reels by UGC, as these are approximately six times more numerous than the ones generated by owned brands.

The main theoretical implications of this study point out that contrary to what has been continuously stated in the scientific literature on the positive incidence of the use of celebrities in advertising (e.g., Hoffman and Tan, 2013, 2015; Klucharev et al., 2008; Ohanian, 1990; Sung et al., 2018; Till and Shimp, 1998), in this exploratory study the posts from owned media with the presence of celebrities and influencers did not generate greater interaction than those in which they did not appear. In fact, some posts made by non-professional UGC achieved greater reach and interaction, which could begin to highlight the relativity of the effect of the use of influencers in these types of campaigns, or that these campaigns are not correctly defining the celebrity or influencer concerning the target audience of the campaign or the platform.

Data availability

The data that support the findings of this study are openly available in *Zenodo* at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7945352>.

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Note

1 Instagram's algorithms use different factors to determine the relevance of a content, including interactions received (likes and comments), the content of the post itself and hashtags.

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Author contributions

Conceptualization, LMRR, JDBC; methodology, LMRR, BCA; software, JATC; validation, LMRR, BCA; formal analysis, JDBC, BCA; investigation, LMRR, JDBC, BCA; resources, JDBC; data curation, BCA; writing—original draft preparation, BCA, LMRR; writing—review and editing, LMRR, JDBC; visualization, JATC; supervision, LMRR; project administration, JDBC; funding acquisition, JDBC. All authors have read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript.

Competing interests

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Ethical approval

Ethical approval is not required as the study did not involve human participants.

Informed consent

Ethical approval is not required as the study did not involve human participants.

Additional information

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